

Optimum seedling age for transplanting short-duration rice

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Field experiments in 1978-79 used short-duration rice variety IET1444 (Rasi) to determine the optimum age at which to transplant seedlings and to test plant spacing. Three seedling ages (25, 40, 55 d) and three spacings (10 × 10, 15 × 10, 20 × 10 cm) were tested in the main plots. Two nitrogen levels (100 and 150 kg/ha) and 2 nursery methods were in the subplots.

Plant height, productive tillers/hill, and panicle length were not adversely affected by transplanting up to 40-d-old seedlings. With 55-d-old seedlings, those characters were significantly affected. Spacing of 20 × 10 cm was best (see table), regardless of seedling age. Semidry nursery and 150 kg N/ha produced better growth and yield. Grain yield of 25- and 40-d-old seedlings differed insignificantly. □

Growth and yield of IET1444 at different transplanting ages.

Treatment	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled spikelets (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Daily production (kg/ha)
<i>Seedling age</i>						
25 d	73	8	8	73	5.1	57
40 d	78	8	17	74	5.0	59
55 d	72	6	16	63	3.9	49
<i>Spacing</i>						
10 × 10 cm	74	7	17	68	4.7	55.2
15 × 10 cm	74	7	17	71	4.7	55.9
20 × 10 cm	75	8	17	71	4.6	54.4
<i>Nitrogen level</i>						
100 kg/ha	73	7	17	69	4.5	53.2
150 kg/ha	76	8	17	71	4.8	57.2
<i>Nursery method</i>						
Wet	73	7	17	67	4.6	53.7
Semidry	75	7	17	72	4.8	56.5
CD at 5%						
Seedling age	2.7	0.3	0.4	3.0	0.45	5.2
Spacing	2.7	0.3	ns	ns	ns	ns
Nitrogen level	1.4	0.2	ns	2.0	0.11	1.4
Nursery method	1.4	ns	0.3	2.0	0.11	1.4

Efficiency of Mussoorie rock phosphate in a rice - wheat rotation

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Although ground rock phosphate has been a useful additive for acid soils, its performance in neutral and alkali soils has not been described.

We evaluated the performance of Mussoorie rock phosphate (MRP) in a long-term rice - wheat rotation on a neutral Typic Haplustalf at PAU farm, beginning in 1976 kharif. MRP has 10.2% P, of which only 0.9% is citrate soluble. Soil was a loam with pH 7.4, electrical conductivity 0.20 mmho/cm, 0.40% organic carbon, 4 ppm Olsen's extractable P, and 75 ppm available K.

A basal dose of 120 kg N/ha as urea and 50 kg K/ha as muriate of potash was applied (see table). To increase the effi-

ciency of MRP, pyrite (FeS) five times that of MRP was added in all MRP treatments. Treatments were in a randomized block design with three replications.

For rice, P and K were applied at transplanting. N was applied in equal splits at transplanting and 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. For wheat, P, K, and 1/2 N were drilled at sowing, and the remaining N was applied before the first irrigation. Grain yield was recorded each year and the effect of P treatment on rice and wheat yield is in the table.

Rice yields after P treatments were slightly more than control yields, but the differences were not significant. The application of superphosphate to wheat at 26.2 kg P/ha increased yields significantly over the control. MRP treatments did not yield as well as superphosphate treatments. This was due to a decrease in soil pH from 7.4 to 5.7 under 52.4 kg P from MRP and a decrease from 7.4 to 6.3 under 39.3 from MRP during the aerobic conditions of wheat cultivation. □

Effect of phosphorus treatments on rice and wheat grain yields, Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Av of six crops	
	Unhusked rice (t/ha)	Wheat (t/ha)
P ₀	6.3	2.1
P _{26.2} (SP) ^a	6.6	2.5
P _{26.2} (MRP) ^b	6.4	2.1
P _{26.2} (¼ SP + ¾ MRP)	6.5	2.2
P _{13.1} (SP)	6.5	2.4
P _{13.1} (MRP)	6.5	2.2
P _{13.1} (¼ SP + ¾ MRP)	6.5	2.3
P _{52.4} (MRP)	6.4	1.2
P _{52.4} (¼ SP + ¾ MRP)	6.5	1.7
CD at 5%	ns	0.37

^aP_{26.2} SP = 26.2 kg P/ha from single superphosphate. ^bP_{26.2} MRP = 26.2 kg P/ha from MRP.

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